

Effect of Teaching Practice on Self Confidence of Would Be Secondary School Teachers

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Abstract Self-confidence is an individual feature, it is the positive assessment of one's own skills and abilities to achieve significant goals and meet one's needs. It is an attitude which allows individual to have positive yet realistic view of himself and his situations. The present study was carried out on Self-confidence among would be secondary school teachers to study the effect of teaching practice on the basis of the area they belong to and stream. Survey method was used to collect the data of 80 B.Ed. teacher trainees of Jalandhar region through convenient sampling. The tool used for the study was Agnihotri's Self confidence Inventory (ASCI) developed by Agnihotri and Dr. Rekha Gupta. The results showed that there is positive effect of teaching practice on self confidence of would be teachers.

Keywords Self Confidence, Would be Teachers.

Introduction There are different factors affect learning like interest, motivation, attitudes, problem-solving skills, self confidence, and self sufficiency. Since there is a positive relationship between successes, self-confidence and motivation, having a higher levels of mentioned capabilities increases success and having a lower levels of those diminishes success. This is because when individuals have self confidence, they feel better within the process of learning and higher level of learning is accomplished.

Objective of study 1. To study and compare the self confidence level of would be secondary school teachers from rural and urban areas 2. To study and compare the self confidence of would be secondary school teachers from science and arts stream.

Review of Literature

The basic opinion is that individuals having higher levels of self-confidence are more successful in solving problems that they confront (Owens, 2001). This situation emphasizes the necessity for defining self-confidence which is assumed to have a great effect on learning. Self confidence is answering the question; "How the others are seeing me?" Our perception is always connecting with the others (Baltaş, 2002). Nowadays, research studies show that self-confidence and success are related (Daniel, 2006). Particularly, Fitch (1970) pointed out the relationship between self-confidence and success. In addition, self-confidence is one of the most important factors for motivation and future success. In another research, Hair (2003) found that positive self confidence affects academic success positively.

(Lindblom-Ylänne et al., 2006) consider confidence not as a generic concept but a reflection of the person's perception of their capacity to achieve a particular goal in a specific situation. Therefore the particular teaching context is likely to be central to an individual's level of self-confidence. Some studies do provide insight into the relevance of self-confidence for teaching and teacher development. In one study, two teachers, who were given the lowest rating by students in a law school, were interviewed and observed before and after a programme for improving instruction (Hativa, 2000). Low self-confidence in teaching ability was outlined as a key trait of one of the teachers in the study. As the teachers altered their teaching behaviour, such as speaking more slowly and improving the clarity of the organization of the lesson, self-confidence appeared to improve. However, the findings can only be considered as being preliminary due to the use of only two participants from the same subject area and teaching context. In a study of academics' conceptions of their own development as a teacher, Åkerlind (2003)

identified one way that development was experienced was as an increase in comfort, confidence and ease of teaching. This way of experiencing development was considered to be entirely self-focused, however it did relate to both teacher and student focused understandings of teaching. This provides a slightly different perspective on the role of confidence in teaching, but it does indicate that confidence is an important dimension for development regardless of an individual's conception and approach to teaching. Akbari and Sahubzada (2020) found the effects of self confidence on learning of students in areas of students' participation in seeking goal and development of interest in lessons. Self-confidence fuels optimism and encourages a person to believe in his or her own skills, no matter how difficult the endeavour may be. Bhat (2022) explained that self-confidence motivates people to take chances, try new things, and learn new abilities in order to deal with a difficult circumstances. The majority of the present educational problem is due to poor self-confidence, which has resulted in a lack of adequate involvement and inadequate growth despite spending a significant amount of time in class. Therefore the aim of the current study is to consider the role of self confidence upon the approach to teaching and development as a teacher for a group of new academics.

Methodology Confidence scale was administered on B.Ed students before and after teaching practice. The school teachers went for teaching practice for selected days in selected schools. This is the experiment phase of the study. When student teachers came back to their colleges after teaching practice. Then, self confidence scale was administered as post test by the investigator. Statistical analysis was done to draw the results and interpretations.

Analysis

Result Analysis

Analysis of data on Pre test scores in self confidence level of rural and urban would be school teachers

Scores on self-confidence were collected by using Agnihotri's Self Confidence Inventory. The collected data is tabulated into mean and standard deviation.

Table 1.1 showing Pre test scores on self confidence level of rural and urban student

Area	N	Mean	S.D
Rural	60	29.80	11.38
Urban	60	25.08	10.42

Table 1.1 indicates mean scores and standard deviations on self-confidence level of rural and urban would be secondary school teachers. The mean score of pre test of self confidence level of rural would be secondary school teachers is 29.90 with standard deviation 11.38 and mean score of pre test of self confidence level of urban student teachers is 25.07 with standard deviation 10.42. Self confidence level is more in rural would be secondary school teachers.

Analysis of data on Post test scores in self confidence level of rural and urban would be secondary school teachers

Table 1.2 showing Post test scores in self confidence level of rural and urban would be secondary school teachers

Area	N	Mean	S.D
Rural	60	32.76	13.7
Urban	60	35.35	13.4

Table 1.2 indicates mean scores and standard deviations on self confidence level of rural and urban student teachers The mean score of post test of self confidence level of rural student teachers is 32.76 with standard deviation 13.7 and mean score of pre test of self confidence of urban student teachers is 35.35 with standard deviation 13.4. Post test scores showed that self confidence level is more in urban would be secondary school teachers.

Analysis of data on Pre test scores in Self-confidence level of arts and science would be secondary school teachers

Table 1.3 showing Pre test scores in self confidence level of arts and science would be secondary school teachers

Area	N	Mean	S.D
Arts	60	28.83	11.54
Science	60	26.13	10.64

Table 1.3 indicates mean scores and standard deviations on self confidence level of arts and science would be secondary school teachers. The mean score of pre test of self confidence level of arts would be secondary school teachers is 28.83 with standard deviation 11.54 and mean score of pre test of self confidence level of science student teachers is 26.13 with standard deviation 10.64. Self- Confidence level of arts would be secondary school teachers is more.

Analysis of data on Post test scores in Self-confidence level of Arts and Science would be secondary school teachers

Table 1.4 showing Post test scores in self confidence level of Arts and Science would be secondary school teachers

Area	N	Mean	S.D
Arts	60	31.15	12.79
Science	60	36.90	13.80

Table 1.4 indicates mean scores and standard deviations on self confidence level of arts and science would be secondary school teachers. The mean scores of post test of self confidence level of arts would be secondary school teachers is 31.15 with standard deviation 12.79 and mean scores of post test of self confidence level of science student teachers is 36.90 with standard deviation 13.80. Self -confidence level is more in science would be secondary school teachers.

Analysis of data on scores in Self-Confidence level of rural and urban would be secondary school teachers

Table showing mean, S.D & t-value on scores of self confidence level

N	Scores of Self confidence	Mean	S.D	SEm	t-test
120	Post scores	34.03	13.56	1.238	4.135
120	Pre scores	27.48	11.13	1.017	

Above table depicts that mean of post scores is 34.03 with standard deviation 13.56 and mean of pre scores is 27.48 with standard deviation 11.13. t-value is 4.135 which is significant at 0.01 level. There is difference in pre scores and post scores of self confidence of would be secondary school teachers.

Conclusion In the light of hypothesis, Teaching practice has a significant effect on self-confidence level of B.Ed students" is accepted, Further mean scores of post test is more than mean scores of post test. It means the treatment has increased the self confidence level of B.Ed students.

Suggestions for the future Study There is always a scope for more research in a particular field. The present study also leaves ample scope to carry on further meaningful research. Here are some suggestions for future research projects.

- 1.The present study focused solely on B.Ed Students from Jalandhar district only. A similar study may be carried on other districts and states also.
2. A comparative study can be undertaken among senior secondary teachers teaching in different schools.
3. The study can be undertaken on gender basis.
4. The purpose of the present study was to find out the effect of teaching practice on self confidence. Research can be conducted on various other variables like motivation, self efficacy, organizational climate etc.

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